

ISic0301

Inscription recording restoration of a nymphaeum

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2017.06.29

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 539

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 53 cm

Width 72 cm

Depth 3 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Dilapsummultor]um i n̄ [cur] ja nymfeum [et]
2. [magnal] abe foedatum cuius etiam aqua
3. [inductano]vo meatu tamen corruptione
4. [fistularu]m ita fuerat poll ȳ ȳa ut quanda m
5. [pernicie]m haurientibȳ inferre videretur
6. [indulgenti]a · Fl (avi) · Arsini v (iri) c (larissimi) · consularis · p (rovinciae)
· S (iciliae) ·
7. [restitut]um adque usui populi splendidissi mae
8. [urbisCatinaeite---]m redditum reformatumque est.
9. [Cur]ante · Fl (avio) · Ambrosio · v (iro) · p (erfectissimo) · d · pr

Apparatus

The restorations are those proposed by Manganaro, except for the divergences noted below

Manganaro: splendidissimi; lapis: splendidissimae

Manganaro: Catinensium

Manganaro: d(ecurionum) [d(ecreto) a]er(e) p(ublico)

Translation (en)

The nymphaeum, ruined by the neglect of many and disfigured by a great collapse, and whose waters,
 although brought in by a new supply, yet had become so polluted by the decay of the pipes that they
 seemed to bring some ruin on those that drank them, by the favour of the most noble Flavius
 Arsinius, consular governor of the province of Sicily, has been restored and given back for the use
 of the most splendid people of Catania, and it has been restructured. The work was overseen by the
 most perfect Flavius Ambrosius, by decree of the town councillors, at public expense.

Translation (it)

Il ninfeo, rovinato dall'abbandono di molti e disfatto da un grande crollo, e le cui acque, benché
 fornite da una nuova offerta, erano ancora così inquinate dal decadimento dei tubi che sembravano
 portare malanni su quelli che le bevevano, per il favore del più nobile Flavius Arsinius,
 governatore consolare della provincia di Sicilia, è stato restaurato e restituito per l'uso delle
 più splendide persone di Catania, ed è stato ristrutturato. Il lavoro è stato supervisionato dal più
 perfetto Flavius Ambrosius, con decreto dei consiglieri comunali, a spese pubbliche.

Commentary

An earlier Greek text on the other side of this stone (ISic0649) records the original construction of the nymphaeum, the repair of which is recorded in this later Latin text. Flavius Ambrosius is mentioned by Symmachus, having been sent as a legate to the imperial court by the provincial council of Sicily (c.377-379 AD). Flavius Arsinius, could be identical with an Arsenius who was praised by Emperor Constantius II in 359 AD, and if so would have been governor of Sicily perhaps in the early 350s AD. It is possible that the collapse of the nymphaeum was connected to the major earthquake and tsunami of 365 AD. The stone bearing the earlier inscription was re-used in order to record the restoration. It is possible that it was displayed in such a way as to show both sides, but this is not common.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175828

EDR 074190
EDCS 21900336

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